

DO1 report for Dellinger project

21 Feb 2017

The DO1 deliverable for Dellinger is to provide the basic information on the environments and user requirements at the partner sites that will allow an adequate technical plan for the development of the DO2 deliverable. The process used was to carry out a set of discussions with the project members from the national providers for their respective sites and prepare a report from those discussions. The report has been reviewed by the project members and is considered to be accurate as of the writing of the report.

An important caveat is that each of the respective national providers continues to advance their technologies, policies and implementations. This means that it will be necessary to modify and update the plans as the national providers move forward with their own plans.

A second caveat is that the approach taken in this document is to consider resource sharing in the context of the HPC resources available through the national providers. This is one dimension of resource sharing but it has a direct bearing on other resources, such as user support and storage resources. These other resources are only considered in the context of the HPC resource sharing. Other projects that depend on resource sharing for their success include Tryggve and Glenna and discussions will be necessary to understand the possible alignments between these projects as future use cases. These efforts should be considered in the later phase of the Dellinger project.

The third caveat is that the project is intended to outline the framework for resource sharing based on a small number of use cases. It is expected that these use cases will provide a solid basis for proceeding and that potentially more complex arrangements may evolve in the future, e.g., working with domain specific projects that are currently in the planning or early development stages. Items 5 and 6 are to be expanded on as part of DO3.

Finally, a set of general principles are considered to underlie the project and these are discussed in the following document:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1f2IOVYma83oEmOsaOMbeYHqEMMpCgd167oDRjEhXH7I/edit>

Use Cases

There are two use cases considered in the early stages of the project, but it is expected that more will materialize as a result of the plans in DO2. The first is a very high level of

strategic coordination on future systems that was outlined by Jacko Koster. The second use case is a user driven case that is also a NeIC project, which should provide the possibility of extensive in-depth interaction.

- a. Strategic coordination on future systems
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1CRqvcj3myBTulUHCvNEPyMxJLcCnHg69YKAgZX4zkno/edit?usp=sharing>
- b. Nordic Language Processing Lab
https://wiki.neic.no/wiki/Nordic_Language_Processing_Laboratory

The vision of the NeIC project "Nordic Language Processing Laboratory" is to implement a digital Nordic laboratory for Natural Language Processing (NLP) by piloting innovative ways to share HPC and data resources across country borders, by pooling competency in expert support teams and within the user community, and by enabling internationally competitive, data-intensive research and experimentation. Instead of providing only an incomplete sets of standard tools and datasets on several resources, the partners aim at establishing a well-defined uniform platform for NLP research by installing and maintaining commonly needed tools and datasets on every resource of the laboratory to be shared by Nordic NLP researchers.

DO1 components

Norway:

Expectation for the deliverable:

1. Current usage modes for non-national users
 - a. co-PIs: Sigma2 would define the non-national users in the user database (MAS), which is a common database (django db) that all of the national systems use. Users apply by an electronic form (<https://www.metacenter.no/user/application/>), after which Sigma2 and the PI have to acknowledge the application by logging into MAS and confirm the application. The creation of the users on the systems is automatic on the system side.
 - b. PRACE: there are two types of accounts associated with PRACE Tier-1 projects. If the users are doing a project together with people working on a PRACE project, then the same process is used as above. In the second case, the system administrator of the Tier-1 system in Oslo gets the information from the PRACE LDAP and feeds it into MAS. User accounts are created similarly to normal NOTUR accounts, however, some changes are applied (e.g., no direct ssh login via frontend nodes, but login with

- x.509 certificates via a special login node). The process requires some manual steps.
- c. guest accounts - These users are defined locally by the system administrators.
 - d. test accounts - same as guest accounts.
2. An analysis of current computational capacities - the current operational hardware for the Norwegian national research community is described at : <https://www.sigma2.no/content/hpc-hardware-resources>
- a. Fram is the incoming system, <https://www.sigma2.no/Fram> This system is expected to be operational on 18 April 2017.
 - b. There is a proposal before the Norwegian research council for a new system, with an expected end-2018 installation.
3. Projections of future capabilities for making resources available will be conducted for the period of 2016-2020.
- a. The national computing environment is moving from having four systems (2 supercomputers, 2 data centric systems) to one system that is a general purpose system and one system that is a large supercomputer.
 - b. The process for determining what a prospective system should be has been based on the aggregation of the usage of the systems and matching the anticipated future usage against vendor roadmaps. The expected usage was weighted by the usage levels of the range of applications, with consideration given to the largest areas of usage. There are a limited number of large user groups and a large number of smaller users with a wide range of applications. To complement this, a user survey was done to help guide the procurement.
 - c. Fram (A1) is the replacement for the two of four systems currently in use.
 - d. There is a two year cycle for funding of replacement systems. Currently, there is a funding proposal before the Research Council of Norway for a system (B1) that would be a replacement for the remaining two oldest systems in end-2018. Fram (A1) and the coming replacement system (B1) will be the two systems covering the 2017-2020 time period.
 - e. UNINETT/Sigma2 has estimated that the aggregated demand for HPC resources at the national level for the period 2018-2021. The estimates are based on extrapolation of usage data for the period 2012-2015, combined with user surveys. In the user surveys, PI/projects were asked to provide estimates for the period 2018-2020. The user surveys resulted in a low and a high estimate for the period. The conclusion from this forecast is that the new system Fram (A1) needs to be increased with around 20% more cores around 2017/18. The new system B1 will require 45 000 cores.

4. Pilot projects will be identified and used to define the user requirements.
 - a. NLPL pilot project
 - b. Additional pilots to be identified in phase 2
5. Possible avenues for meeting the requirements based on projected capabilities
6. Relevant phase 2 delivery objects will be defined, including staffing.

Denmark

Expectation for the deliverable:

1. Current usage modes for non-national users
 - a. co-PIs:
 - b. PRACE: none
 - c. guest accounts:
 - d. test accounts:
 - e. There is no effective difference between different of types users but there is a difference the processes for adding users at SDU and DTU. SDU uses the edugain system, <https://deic-adm.sdu.dk/admin/?edugain=1>, to allow logins to Abacus 2.0 for any user with a home university that is part of the edugain system. This includes users at universities outside of Denmark. If the university is not part of edugain, adding a user is a manual process. DTU relies on a manual process to add users to the Computerome system. User information is not shared between SDU and DTU, which is not currently an issue as there aren't many overlaps in users. There is an internal DK reference group for HPC that meets every 3-4 months.
2. An analysis of current computational capacities
 - a. The Abacus 2.0 system became operational in 2015 and is expected to have a lifetime of 4 years and is to be turned off mid 2019. Information on the system is available at <https://abacus.deic.dk/> This is a general purpose HPC system for use by researchers at Danish institutions and by industry with appropriate funding arrangements.
 - b. Computerome is the Danish national life sciences system described at http://wiki.bio.dtu.dk/computerome/index.php/Main_Page and is not expected to be part of the initial resource sharing project but may be included in the later work.
3. Projections of future capabilities for making resources available will be conducted for the period of 2016-2020.
 - a. There are currently discussions on the possible renewal of DeIC and part of these discussions relate to the future of HPC in Denmark. The final

plans for this are expected to be known by early 2018. The current plans are to turn off both Danish supercomputers, Computerome and Abacus 2.0 in mid 2019, and to buy new supercomputers at the same time but that is entirely dependent on the outcomes of the discussions. Computerome is currently expanding.

4. Pilot projects will be identified and used to define the user requirements.
 - a. There is presently the opportunity for small research groups to get small allocations on either of the two national systems to test their applications and then to buy in to access the system.
<https://abacus.deic.dk/get-access/deic-pilot>
 - b. This remains to be defined for international pilot projects.
5. Possible avenues for meeting the requirements based on projected capabilities
6. Relevant phase 2 delivery objects will be defined, including staffing.

Finland

Expectation for the deliverable:

1. Current usage modes for non-national users
 - a. co-PIs: CSC uses HAKA authentication for applying for a new project, for international users this would need to be handled through the CSC Service Desk. Standard procedure at this time is that there is a PI from Finland. An international account can be applied for separately, but there is still the requirement that the PI needs to be from Finland.
 - b. PRACE: Within PRACE, the Tier-1 exchange, i.e. DECI (Distributed European Computing Initiative), projects and accounts are created in PRACE LDAP by the home site of the project. These are propagated to other sites. At CSC, the relevant data of the accounts is copied to the CSC LDAP each day automatically after the projects to be opened at CSC have been specified.
 - c. guest accounts - No
 - d. test accounts: No, but in principle possible to provide ad-hoc small amount of access.
 - e. The exchange of resources is expected to be acceptable with some constraints. Resources can be provided to others if Finnish researchers get an exchange of access to the equivalent resources in the other country. This is already covered by an agreement with Ministry of Education and Culture from 2009, and is valid for time being.

- f. As long as there is a 1 to 1 exchange, there should be no problem. When exchange done in different periods of time, e.g., Finland gives out the resources in 2017 and is expected to receive equivalent back in 2018 - it requires further discussion, considering topics like VAT etc.
2. An analysis of current computational capacities

The current resources are described at <https://research.csc.fi/csc-s-servers>
 3. Projections of future capabilities for making resources available will be conducted for the period of 2016-2020.
 - a. There is not a decision regarding funding of future computational capacity but negotiations with the Ministry of Education and Culture ongoing.
 - b. The graph for 1993-2016 is available and future capabilities may be projected from that.

4. Pilot projects will be identified and used to define the user requirements.
 - a. It would good to have at least 1 PI from Finland for any pilot projects that involve Finnish resources. According to the agreement with the Ministry of Education and Culture, resource exchange projects require the approval of the director of the Services for Research unit at CSC.
 - b. User requirement: academic usage strongly preferred.

- c. Academic users if PI from outside, but exceptions can be considered on the CSC management level (if needed).
 - d. Everything is in English for researchers to be able to apply. The researchers do not need to physically sign any documents and all steps are electronic.
 - e. It is important to provide updates to the customer panel as this progresses.
 - f. Ministry of Education and Culture should be involved/informed, as the exchange of the resources has been done at the same period of time so far.
5. Possible avenues for meeting the requirements based on projected capabilities
 6. Relevant phase 2 delivery objects will be defined, including staffing.

Iceland

Expectation for the deliverable:

1. Current usage modes for non-national users
 - a. co-PIs: -
 - b. PRACE: none
 - c. guest accounts: -
 - d. test accounts: -
 - e. The Nordic HPC system was operated in collaboration with Norway, Sweden and Denmark and included users from each of those countries. Projects have only one person as the leader but there are no restrictions from having more than one (co-PIs).
2. An analysis of current computational capacities
 - a. IS does not currently operate a national system but has NHPC at University of Iceland and the joint computer at University of Iceland and University of Reykjavik. There is previous experience with the NHPC system, Garðar, that is relevant. The current systems are described at <http://ihpc.hi.is/>
3. Projections of future capabilities for making resources available will be conducted for the period of 2016-2020.
 - a. There is not an activity in place for replacing Garðar. There has been an opportunistic approach to expand the joint computer which has not been able to gather funding.
 - b. Any approach will need backing from the steering group because the University of Iceland representatives cannot make any commitments on a national level. RHnet operates at the national level.

- c. Within the university, the funding applications go through the national research funding agency, Rannis:
<http://eeagrants.org/Partnerships/Donor-programme-partners/Icelandic-Centre-for-Research-Rannis>
- 4. Pilot projects will be identified and used to define the user requirements.
- 5. Possible avenues for meeting the requirements based on projected capabilities
- 6. Relevant phase 2 delivery objects will be defined, including staffing.

Sweden

- 1. Current usage modes for non-national users, e.g. co-PIs, PRACE, guests

Foreign researchers may be co-investigators on projects created via SUPR - SNIC User and Project Repository (<https://supr.snlic.se/>) for SNIC projects, foreign researchers may hence create accounts.

To be able to apply for and receive allocations on SNIC resources as a PI the applicant must be affiliated to a by the Swedish research Council approved custodian of funds, which includes academia and research institutes. Furthermore, applicants need to fulfil the requirements in terms of position, i.e. doctoral student, professor et.al. which is required for a specific type of allocation of compute time.

- 2. An analysis of current computational capacities

SNIC provides HPC-resources via six SNIC partner centers. Each center owns and operates SNIC HPC-resources, which are replaced within 4-5 years. The table below lists some characteristics of the current HPC-resources. Each resource consists of a compute resource (a number of compute nodes, each with a number of CPUs and internal shared-memory, plus an interconnect that connects the nodes).

System name	SNIC centre	System type	#nodes, #cores, #cores/node, memory/node, etc	Interconnect	Until (est)

Abisko	HPC2N	cluster	318 nodes, 15264 cores, 4x 12 cores/node, 308x 128 GB and 10x 512 GB	InfiniBand	02/2018
Aurora	Lunarc	cluster	180 nodes, 3600 cores, 2x 10 cores/node, 64 GB/node	InfiniBand	12/2019
Beskow	PDC	Cray XC40	1676 nodes, 53632 cores, 2x 16 cores/node, 64 GB/node	Cray Aries	12/2019
Hebbe	C3SE	cluster	315 nodes; 6300 cores; 2x 10 cores/node; 252 x 64 GB, 46 x 128 GB, 7 x 256 GB, 3 x 512 GB, 1 x 1024 GB, 4x 64 GB RAM + 1 NVIDIA K40 GPU, 2 x 256 GB RAM + NVIDIA k4200 for remote graphics	InfiniBand	12/2019

Kebnekaise	HPC2N	cluster	<p>524 nodes total:</p> <p>432 nodes Intel Broadwell E5-2690v4, 2x14 cores, 128 GB/node;</p> <p>20 nodes, 3TB/node, Intel Broadwell E7-8860v4, 4x18 cores;</p> <p>32 nodes with 2x NVIDIA K80; 4 nodes with 4x NVIDIA K80; 128 GB/node;</p> <p>36 nodes, Intel Knights Landing 7250 SKU (68 cores, 1.4 Ghz/1.2 Ghz/AVX), 192 GB/node</p>	InfiniBand EDR/FDR	12/2020
Rackham	UPPMAX	cluster	304 nodes, 6080 cores, 2 x 10 cores/node, 274 x 128 GB, 30 x 256 GB	Infiniband	01/2021
Triolith	NSC	cluster	1600 nodes, 25600 cores, 2 x 8 cores/node, 1544 x 32 GB/node, 56 x 128 GB/node	InfiniBand	06/2018